

ROBS4CROPS

D1.9 Farmers perception on the proposed and running agricultural robotic systems (4)

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D1.9 Farmers perception on the proposed and running agricultural robotic systems (4)

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Abstract:	This document presents the perception of robotic systems for weeding application by farmers, on technical aspects. One co-design session was held in each of the four Large-scale pilots, from which the data presented in this document has been extracted. It contains a description of how the discussions were held, what subjects on the different robotic solutions have been covered and the conclusions associated to them, and ways of improvements that will allow the project and external stakeholders to improve said robotic solutions. This deliverable D1.8 will mainly be used by partners in WP1 in this project, roboticists and external stakeholders, to know what needs to be improved on the robotic solutions that are experimented with in this project, in order to fit the farmer's needs and reach field maturity (TRL7).

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ROBS4CROPS Consortium			
Participant Number	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
2	GIROPOMA COSTA BRAVA SL	GIR	ES
3	AGROTIKOS SYNETAIRISMOS POLISEOS XIRON KAI NOPON STAFYLION KIATOY KORINTHIAS PIGASOS	PEG	GR
4	SERRATER SL	SER	ES
5	SMART AGRI TECHNOLOGY BV	SAT	NL
6	TERRENA SOCIETE COOPERATIVE AGRICOLE	TER	FR
7	ABEMEC BV	ABE	NL
8	AGREENCULTURE	AGC	FR
9	AGRO INTELLIGENCE APS	AI	DK
10	FOODSCALE HUB ENTREPRENEURSHIP ANDINNOVATION ASSOCIATION	FSH	SR
11	TEYME TECHNOLOGIE AGRICOLA SL	TEY	ES
12	GEPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON	AUA	GR
13	FUNDACIO EURECAT	EUT	ES
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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
CoDS	Co-Design Session
EU	European Union
EUT	Eurecat
FR	France
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIR	Giropoma
GR	Greece
LSP	Large Scale Pilot
NL	Netherlands
PDL	Permissioned Distributed Ledger
R4C	Robots4Crops
RaaS	Robot as a Service
ROI	Return On Investment
SER	Serrater
SP	Spain
TER	Terrena
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

Rob4Crops aims to create a high-end agricultural robotic system. In the project, this system will be used for spraying and mechanical weeding, but the aim is that the system will ultimately support other applications in the field as well. An unmanned ground vehicle (UGV), robot or tractor, will carry the smart implements (sprayers and weeders), which will use the standard 3-point linkage and communicate with ISOBUS and TIM. The Farming Controller (planning software) supervises the system with Digital Twin technology and the data, which are going to be collected by UGVs and implements, will be saved in a Farm Management Information System (FMIS). This robotic system will allow farmers to plan agricultural tasks remotely. Selecting a specific implement, farmers will be able to proceed with the appropriate vehicle for their operation at their field. They will supervise the executed activity through the simulation environment of the farming controller in real-time. All the data will be visible and therefore, farmers will be able to intervene and customize the system's operation if the situation necessitates.

The aforementioned methodology will be adapted and implemented in the context of four Large-Scale Pilots (LSPs), farmers' field where the robotics systems are tested.

Co-design sessions can be round tables, or discussions held with voluntary participants such as farmers, and aim to collect data and opinions on the robotic systems. The collected data is then used by other project partners (especially roboticists) to improve their products.

Co-design sessions were held through the entire project. This document gives the results of the co-design sessions held in 2024, and thus provides the perception by farmers on latest robotic systems for weeding (mechanical or spraying) and disease control (spraying). This document is organized as follows. Four methods to collect data on farmer perception are given in section 2. In section 3, the farmer perception is developed and ends with a few requirements. Finally, an analysis of those perceptions is presented as a conclusion.

2 Structure & Methods of each Co-Design Session

2.1. Topics

The topics addressed in the co-design sessions in 2023 included technical issues (such as specification of requirements) as well as non-technical issues (such as regulations and economics).

LSP1 (FR) : Technical matters – User’s experience

What did the winegrowers think of :

- The new RX-20-H that Pellenc and Terrena’s subsidiary LVVD is about to commercialize
- The Manual remote control of the robot
- The mobile App “Automate”

And how can it be improved ?

LSP2 (GR) : Technical matters – User’s experience and overall use of the robot in the LSP

What did the users think of :

- Using an autonomous solution for spraying apples orchards in Spain
- The autonomous tractor itself

LSP3 (SP) : Technical matters – User’s experience and overall use of the robot in the LSP

What did the users think of :

- Using an autonomous solution for spraying grapes in Greece
- The autonomous tractor itself

LSP4 (NL) : Technical matters - Usability of the robot and the working tools

What did Dutch arable farmers think of the autonomous solutions:

- The Agrolntelli Robotti
- The working capacity of the machine
- The autonomous capabilities of the implement
- What can be solution to create autonomous platforms that work together with the implements.

2.2. Type of stakeholders and participants

LSP 1 (FR) :

Table 1 - Type of stakeholder, Organisation and name of the participants of the 2024 LSP1 CoDS

Stakeholders	Organisation	Attendees
Organizer	Terrena (TER)	Ludovic PATTE
		Luc DEJONGHE
Participants	Farmers	10 winegrowers
	LVVD	2 advisors

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LSP 4 (NL) :

Table 4 - Type of stakeholder, Organisation and name of the participants of the 2024 LSP4 CoDS

Stakeholders	Organisation	Attendees
Organizer	Abemec BV	Nard Savelkouls
		Luuk Banken
Participants	More than 15 000 participants to the event. Families, farmers, and students	

2.3. Structure and organisation

LSP1 (FR) :

Date	04/12/2024
Duration	4 hours
Structure	10:30 (15 mins) : welcoming the farmers 10:45 (35 mins) : presentation of the RX-20 robot and open discussion 11:20 (1 hours) : Demonstration of the robot weeding in large-row vines 15:30 (1 hours 30 mins) : Users' experience tests and open discussion

LSP4 (NL) :

Date	21/11/2024 to 24/11/2024
Duration	4 days
Structure	Abemec Open Days

LSP 1 (FR)

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Figure 1 - Pictures of some LSP 2024 CoDS

3 Results

All following information is categorised depending on its type :

Feedback / Farmers opinions

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

3.1. The robotic solution

3.1.1. The CEOL robot

3.1.1.1. What did the farmers think of the current model ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

Overall

- The compact and light architecture of the robot is its biggest feature.

The level of trust the farmers put in the robot

- In the first years, farmers want to work beside the robot on field tasks (such as pruning), IT or administrative tasks, to be able to monitor it. They don't fully trust it.

The CEOL work capacity

- The current CEOL robot would not be able to handle both inter-row and inter-vine work at the same time on heavy-soil or steep plots.
 - But this issue is not a big deal for farmers, as the main work the robot needs to accomplish is in the inter-vine.

- Farmers are curious to see the robot working on difficult soils.

The current CEOL robot is very climate-dependant : in dry conditions, it will have a harder time working compared to a tractor. On the other hand, it can get back to the plot more quickly in humid conditions, due to its lighter impact on the ground.

- This issue should be improved with the Pellenc robot, as it will use a more powerful engine.

The after-sale

- The winegrowers feel the need for support and after-sales service for the robot.
 - LVVD (Terrena's subsidiary) intends to put it in place.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

- Farmers asked about the dimensions of the CEOL robot and those of its successor, the RX-20-H from Pellenc.
 - The width comes into 3 options, identical for the 2 robots

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Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.1.1.2. How to improve it ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

Overall, the vision of the final product

- Above all, farmers want a reliable and simple robot. Then the best would be to have access to modules and accessories to improve the robot, and make it fit the farmer's needs.
- Farmers would like the robot to have a high degree of autonomy, with a robot that detects issues and tries to solve them by itself when possible (examples : double-checking bumper alerts ; reversing the robot to remove obstructions such as clods and crop residue from the implements).

Energy autonomy

- For a diesel engine robot, 12h minimum. Plus, such a machine only needs to be refilled to be able to work 24h/24.
 - It is already the case, as the CEOL has an average autonomy >17h
- For an electric robot, farmers have a hard time finding the best solution.
 - With interchangeable batteries, a minimum of 4h of working time per battery. Which means farmers would need with 2 batteries minimum (depending on the charging time of the batteries).
 - For a consolidated vineyard, the ideal would be to have 1 or 2 batteries for a full workday (or a local charging station).
 - For a dispersed vineyard, the ideal would be to work with multiple smaller batteries, changed for fresh ones each time it is moved between plots.
 - For a vineyard cut in isolated blocks, the best would be to have local charging stations.

A possible evolution in a fully electric robot

- Overall, a full electric robot would be a great advantage for some farmers.
- For most farmers, the main interest of a fully electric robot is to reduce their carbon footprint.
The noise reduction is a secondary interest.
- But charging an electric robot can be difficult for some farmers : it depends on their farm's structure, the distance between their plots, etc.
Some farmers are not sure that an easy solution is feasible : it is illegal for a robot to drive on public roads, often preventing the robot from driving to a charging station by itself.
 - It is something on which the recent "Grand Défi de la Robotique Agricole", a project supported by the French government, is going to work on.

Work quality

- Some farmers have experienced issues with the light weight of the tools the current CEOL robot can carry, which reduces the quality of the weeding.
 - The new Pellenc RX-20-H robot should be able to carry heavier tools and should thus answer this issue.

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- Farmers expressed the need to have a robot equipped with an implement capable of adjusting the height of its tools automatically, as it would increase the weeding quality by a lot on tilted plots, or plots which have an uneven ground.
 - This is not part of the 2024 Robs4Crops project experiments on LSP1 anymore.
- Some tools need high speeds (8 – 9km/h) to work properly, but the robot can legally only work at 6 km/h maximum.
 - This issue reduces the flexibility and usability of the robot compared to a tractor.
- The robot needs to be able to plough the inter-vines to be defined as “field-ready” (= TRL7), which has not been fully demonstrated yet, especially on narrow vines. In addition, farmers stated that if the robot can plough, it can carry out any weeding task.

Work monitoring

- Having visual feedback on the robot’s work is essential for farmers.
 - The new RX-20 Pellenc robot is equipped with 4 cameras for a 360° vision, and thus meets this need.
- Some farmers prefer cameras to be low (lower than those of the Pellenc robot), to be able to have a good view of the tools and adjust their height.
 - But that raises an issue, as the cameras could get dirty quickly, thus making them useless.

Other farmers prefer to have a global view of the surroundings and the robot (which the Pellenc robot offers). But would still like to see a camera added behind the tools, at the implement’s height.

- On the implement of the robot, farmers are interested by having “smart” implements, equipped with sensors that can detect blocking of the implements or other type of equipment. But they made it clear that the tools had to remain reliable and durable as much as possible, and that they had to remain tractor-compatible.

Security

- All security measures that could be improved on the CEOL robot are already added to the Pellenc version. Thus farmers don’t need new additions. The main issue remains the impossibility to navigate on communal paths, which border many vineyards. This means that either the regulations need to be changed, or farmers need to reduce the crops’ surfaces to let some space for the robot to navigate their fields.
 - It is something on which the recent “Grand Défi de la Robotique Agricole”, a project supported by the French government, is going to work.
- As a bonus, it would benefit the farmers to have an intercom directly on the robot, to be able quickly talk to people around the robot, to help field colleagues, or to scare off potential troublemakers.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

- What protocol would the robot follow if it encounters a problem overnight ?
 - According to technical experts, the best way to deal with it would be : If the robot faces an issue overnight, it shuts down and pause the ongoing operation for the rest of night (a period defined by the farmer). That way, the farmer doesn’t have to be troubled when he doesn’t want to.

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Security

- Is the robot allowed to run without anybody next to it ?
 - In the fields only.
- Is the robot allowed to drive on communal paths and public roads ?
 - No.

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

- What happens if it rains during an operation, making it difficult ? The robot would need to stop.
 - Maybe adding humidity sensors on the robot would allow it to detect the rain by itself, so it can pause the ongoing operation and resume it later ?
 - Or by linking the robot's computer to the nearest weather station ?

3.1.2. RX-20 robot – Additions to the CEOL feedback

3.1.2.1. What did the farmers think of the current model ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

- The Engine of the robot does sometime have surges, which exist to improve the fuel efficiency, but sometimes it prevents the engine from keeping up when the engine is at its low point (e.g. in steep trajectories). A more linear rate would be better.
- For some farmers, the only tasks the robot needs to accomplish to be considered ready for the market are : Hilling-up, crushing
- Farmers found the robot to be easily taken in hands, and quite useful for their yearly work.
- Farmers trust the autonomous driving of the robot.
- Farmers would need to be trained after buying a robot, in particular on software tools.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

- Would the robot be compatible with a hydraulic crusher ?
 - No, the robot's pump doesn't have enough flow rate. Crushers should be electrical for this model.
Electrical tools have a much better energy efficiency, thus reducing the fuel consumption of the robot when compared to hydraulic tools.
- Will the robot be compatible with de-earthing tools (vineyard ploughs) ?
 - Yes, it will be. As a follow-up to the 2024 co-design session that took place in LSP1 (France), Terrena will test these tools on the RX-20 robot in 2025, along with a towed narrow implement.

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

- What about driving autonomously on local paths ? How can we address it ?
 - The legislation forbids it. Potential solutions :

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Maybe if farmers buy the concerned local paths and then use signs ?

- There is a possible issue with locals that often neglect property trespassing, especially in vines, and who could prevent the robot from working properly.

3.1.2.2. How to improve it ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

- The robot itself could be improved in 3 ways :
 - Improve the track system & add suspensions
 - Add tools sensors, to detect if they become clogged with crop residue or soil clods, or at what rate they operate
 - Add remote supervising
- Overall, improve its versatility

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.1.3. The autonomous tractor

3.1.3.1. What did the farmers think of the current model ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

- In Greece, the current system is not convenient for a lot of fields, which have very narrow edges that are not suitable for autonomous platforms that need space for their U-turn.
- In Greece, they lack Internet connectivity as they have a lot of zones without cellular service.
 - Local partners wish the EU push to improve their internet and cellular coverage.
- The autonomous tractor would allow farmers to reduce human casualties, as they happen often with regular tractors (e.g. vine tractors tipping over in steep plots).
- For Greek farmers, drones are interesting as well, as they can spray in very hard terrain with a high speed.

Human resources

- The technical support of robotic solutions is one of the main issues :
 - Technical users need a hotline with direct contact that can solve most issues.
 - ➔ The response must be quick : for chemical weeding, a breakdown can put a filled tank at risk, and needs to be solved within an hour.
 - Technical users need training to use such a robotic solution.

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- For other users, most issues they have with the autonomous tractor come from the lack of competence of the local labour or farmers.
 - Tractor drivers are not qualified to manage robots on a daily basis, as it requires to have knowledge in software management and electronics systems. Plus, those systems are often interfaced in English, a language that local labour often don't speak.
 - = There is a need to recruit competent dedicated drivers

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.1.3.2. How to improve it ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

- Improve the turn radius of the whole system.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.2. The components of the robotic solution

3.2.1. CEOL and RX-20 – Manual remote

3.2.1.1. What did the farmers think of the current model ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

Ergonomics

- The ergonomics of the manual remote control are important to gain precision and efficiency, especially when weeding with the robot manually. The ergonomics of the CEOL's remote could be improved.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.2.1.2. How to improve it ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

Ergonomics

- An optimal manual remote should look like a drone remote : Small, light, and compact. With the basic controls as analogue buttons, switches and joysticks, but linkable with a smartphone (See picture below).

That way, all the controls are grouped on one platform, with the sturdy navigation controls on the analogue remote, and all the more advanced controls on the digital App of the Smartphone.

Figure 2 - Drone remote controller, discussed during LSP1 co-design session

- The hitch position button of the CEOL's remote controller is not precise enough, it would be better to have an analogue thumbwheel (like the one on the drone controller, see picture below).

Figure 3 - Analogue thumbwheel of a drone remote controller, discussed during LSP1 co-design session

- To answer the question « Can joysticks be replaced by digital controls on a smartphone ? » : no, analogue controller can't be replaced by a fully digital controller, as it needs to be durable enough to withstand any weather : rain, high humidity, low temperatures, mud, etc. It also has to work properly when the user is using gloves.

Range of the remote

- For manual navigation with the analogue controller, a range of 50 – 100 m would be necessary.
- For adjusting the weeding parameters, an unlimited range (using 4G) would be necessary : for some farmers, the ideal solution would be to be able to drive the robot

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on great distances (tele-operation), to unblock it when it encounters an obstacle that is avoidable by a human pilot.

- This aspect has not yet been defined properly within the regulations.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.2.2. CEOL and RX-20 – Digital app

3.2.2.1. What did the farmers think of the current model ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

- The app is doing its job, but it lacks some information that are needed by farmers to work properly, and some essential functionalities.
See part 3.2.2.2. for details on possible improvements.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.2.2.2. How to improve it ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

Displayed information

- It would be very useful to have an easy access to a dashboard similar to the one of a tractor, with the fuel level (or battery charge status), engine temperature, etc.
 - It is important to be able to monitor those parameters regularly.
 - This is a feature that AGC is planning on including in the new version of the App
- It would also be useful to have access to an estimation of the time remaining on an operation, rather than a percentage progress. This would allow them to optimize the time they have to do other tasks in parallel.
- It would be optimal to have multiple levels of use of the App (like the Amazone terminal "AmaTron 4"):
 - Basic mode with base function
 - Intermediate mode,
 - Advanced mode with access to all parameters (including those affecting the integrity of the machine).

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- On a side note, it would also be useful to have access to some "Agrointelligence" data, with sensors on the robot that would detect diseases on the crops, growth zones, missing vine stocks, etc.
- A very useful thing would be to add the possibility to map plots with the "difficulties" the robot encountered in the fields, such as steep slopes or places where the engine has to work harder. It would then allow farmers to know their plots better and adjust the mission.

Farmer's work organisation & efficiency

- It would be essential to keep all the missions' progress saved. It is important to be able to switch from one mission to another without cancelling the previous one. Particularly for the case of managing several parallel missions that have been interrupted by bad conditions (e.g. rain).

= A farmer needs to be able to keep the progress of a mission until he presses the "Done" button.

- The App should memorize the last speed and hitch position parameters of each mission, so the technical agents just have to validate them before starting a mission.

- It would be very important to be able to choose the driving orientation (or navigation direction) before launching the mission, as it increases the weeding quality of the inter-vine work.

Data provision

- It would also be very useful to record all the data acquired during the operations, to allow farmers to make statistical analyses of the work done in the vineyard, to make some comparison between cultivation methods, tools, machines, etc.

Encountering and communicating an error

- If the robot encounters an issue during a mission, farmers need it to notify them quickly : No need for complex information, the optimal solution would be an SMS (that doesn't require a 3G/4G connection) with a quick message setting out the nature of the error = "Tool jammed", or "Obstacle encountered", or "Engine failure" (or redirecting to the app where the error should be explained). With the option of watching the situation with the cameras, then restarting or not restarting the robot if necessary.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.2.3. CEOL and RX-20 – Mission generator

3.2.3.1. What did the farmers think of the current model ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

- The web platform is doing its job, but it lacks some useful functionalities. See part 3.2.3.2. for details on possible improvements.

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Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

3.2.3.2. How to improve it ?

Feedback / Farmers opinions

- The winegrowers would like to be able to set default “pre-recorded” work parameters when generating a mission for the robot. That way, they would be able to quicken the start of each operation, as they would only have to fine-tune each parameter on the field if needed.
- Among those parameters, the working height should be set automatically according to the type of tool used during the mission, and the space it takes.
- It would also be useful to get an estimation of the amount of time the mission will take when generating it, to help farmers organize their work schedule.
- For the land surveying, it would be interesting for some farmers to use the GPS data they have from planting their vines.
It would also be interesting for farmers to be able to modify the cartography of their plot by themselves instead of by the robot’s company, as it would avoid unnecessary costs and time use.

Questions raised by farmers, and answered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

Questions raised by farmers, but unanswered

// No data was extracted from the CoDS for this part //

4 Conclusion & Final analysis

4.1. Main lessons of the 4 years of R4C

On the CEOL and RX-20:

Overall, the architecture of the RX-20 robot is good and addresses the users' requirements that were set in 2021. But it still needs to be improved to reach full maturity.

- Farmers don't fully trust autonomous robots yet, as the technology is new. But they trust the autonomous navigation of the RX-20.
- The RX-20 has yet to prove itself in difficult soils.
 - As part of the project, Terrena (TER) has invested in 2024 in a new implement and news tools to test in 2025 the RX-20 with the hardest weeding task of vineyards : de-earthing with vine ploughs.
- Farmers still feel the need to be supported with using the robot, at least until they get familiar with that technology.
- Farmers want a reliable and simple robot (with modules available to upgrade it), and that is capable of handling simple situations autonomously (weeding operations and avoidable obstacles).
- Farmers are very interested in a fully electric robot (for environmental purposes), but they question its energy autonomy and the current solutions associated with it.
- Farmers want to access more information during the field operations : visual contact with the direct environment of the robot, and visual contact over the implements.
- Farmers would like, if possible, to have the robot analyse its environment to detect diseases or field difficulties in the plots they are working in.

The manual remote control of the CEOL does the job, but its ergonomics could be improved.

- Farmers need something like that of a drone : Small, light, and compact. With the basic controls as analogue buttons, switches and joysticks, but linkable with a smartphone.
- It needs to be easy to be carried around

The digital app of the CEOL robot does the job, but could be improved with the addition of some essential functionalities to reach a mature state.

- Have access to more information about the robot's systems (battery charge level, fuel level, etc.)
- Have access to more information about the on-going mission (mission time remaining)
- Keep all the missions' progress saved until they are finished (crucial to reach field maturity), and recording them afterwards.
- Keep the hitch position and speed parameters saved for each mission, and have users only validate them before starting the mission.
- ➔ *A lot of the farmers' feedback will be addressed with the new version of the app, developed by AGreenCulture.*

The mission generation platform of the CEOL robot does the job, but misses some useful functionalities.

- Setting pre-recorded parameters for every field operations.
- Estimate the time a generated mission will take.
- Farmers need to be able to use the platform themselves.

4.2. What progress compared to 2021

On the CEOL / RX-20 :

Compared to 2021, the CEOL robot has reached a higher degree of maturity in the form of the RX-20 : it is capable of achieving a complete weeding season, almost by itself as it still needs to be monitored (mainly due to the tract system failing or no-GPS zones in plots). Overall, farmers are happy of what the CEOL have become in the form of the RX-20 and what is it capable of, but they still need the robot to become a touch more reliable and autonomous in order to find it "field ready".

On the autonomous tractor :

Compared to previous years, the tractor is now able to drive itself autonomously and its autonomous sprayer has become ready for field use.

But local farmers lack the technical knowledge to take such a robotic solution into their hands.

4.3. What still needs to be addressed to reach field maturity

Overall, on the RX-20 :

- The RX-20 only misses a few points to be "field ready" :
 - o Better track systems
 - o A suspension system to the tracks
 - o Add sensors to its tools
 - o Remote supervision)
- The ergonomics of its manual remote controller
- The information displayed in the Digital App (Mobile app and Misison generation app), and its functionalities, to give the farmer more control over the robot and their work organisation
(should be partially addressed by the newer version of the App)

Additionally, a specific question has not yet been answered during the LSP1 co-design session :

- **What happens if it rains during an operation, making it difficult ?** The robot would need to stop.
Some solutions have been discussed, like the integration of humidity sensors on the robot or a link with a weather station.

4.4. Hindsight on our methods

In 2024

In France and in most other countries, the weather forced the co-design sessions to be postponed or cancelled, originally set in July or in September. As a result, the feedback we got from most some large-scale pilots was incomplete and lacked the feedback of technical users on their robotic solutions.

D1.9 Farmers perception on the proposed and running agricultural robotic systems (4)

Over the 4 years of the project

Globally, the task 1.1 of the Robs4Crops project “ecosystems building” has been a success, thanks to the collaboration of all partners and stakeholders.

The yearly co-design sessions allowed us to create a furnished view of the users’ point of view, which we used through the entire project to improve the robotic systems that we worked on.

This work will carry on after the project, as this deliverable (D1.9 Farmers perception on the proposed and running agricultural robotic systems (4)) and the 2022 report (D1.7 - Farmers perception on the proposed and running agricultural robotic systems (2)) respectively focus on technical feedback (from end-users) and non-technical feedback (from banks, insurances, and government officials). This feedback will be used by roboticists and other technical partners to further improve their products after the project.

Annex 1 – Reference questions to ask during the French 2023 CoDS, based on the users' experience tests organized beforehand

1. The robot
 - What are your needs in terms of robot autonomy (battery/thermal) ?
 - Would a 100% electric robot be a huge advantage ?
 - What level of equipment robustness do you need (track units in particular) ?
 - Would an additional security tool such as a videophone be useful ?
 - Are there any other safety features that you feel could be improved or added ?
 - After 2 years of operation, how could the robot's work be further improved ?

2. The manual remote
 - How can the ergonomics of the radio control be improved ? (size and shape of buttons, shape of the remote).
 - What size and weight should the remote be for your application ?
 - What range should the radio control have for your use ?

3. The AGC smartphone app and the autonomous mode
 - How can you benefit from visual feedback from a camera ?
 - Would having access to the remaining fuel level help you in your organisation ?
 - Would it be useful to know how much time is left on an ongoing mission ?
 - Would it be important to be able to keep track of the progress of an unfinished mission ?
 - Would a history of the tasks carried out with the robot be useful ?
 - What information would you like to have when the robot encounters a problem ?
 - Would it be interesting to be able to choose which way the mission is read before launching it ?
 - Would you like access to more specific information ? (example : engine temperature, engine speed, etc.)

4. The mission generation platform
 - Would it be useful to have a parameter that automatically switches the direction of the mission at each launch ?
 - Would you like to be able to choose the speed of the robot when it is outside the row ?
 - Would it be useful for you to know how long a mission takes before it is generated, when you set the parameters ?
 - Would you like to be able to adjust the hitch position at the beginning and end of the rows ?

5. Conclusion
 - Of all the elements discussed, which would you highlight the most ?
 - What are your favourite features of the CEOL robot so far ?
 - What do you expect from LVVD as a future distributor of the robot ?

Annex 2 –Questions asked during the French 2024 CoDS, along the users’ experience tests

		I totally disagree				I totally agree					
1	I think manual control is easy to use.	1	X	2	3	X	4	5			
2	I imagine that most winegrowers would be able to learn how to use the radio control system quickly.	1		2	3	XX	4	5			
3	I felt that I was in complete control of the robot when I was on manual control.	1	X	2	3	X	4	5			
4	I felt very confident using manual override.	1		2	3	XX	4	5			
5	I found that using the manual override required great concentration.	1		2	XX	3	4	5			
6	I think that using the manual override can lead to dangerous situations.	1		2	X	3	X	4	5		
7	On a scale of 1 to 10, how do you feel you have managed to control the robot manually during the test?	1	2	3	4	5	6	X	8	X	10
8	How do you think the remote control could be improved to make it easier to use?	Ergonomics, sensitivity for turning, easy to transport, compact, range									
9	What would you like to change about the manual control so that it better meets your needs?										
10	Do you have any comments about the manual override: its use, problems encountered during the test, etc.?										

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		I totally disagree			I totally agree						
1	I think the application is easy to use.			X	X						
		1	2	3	4						
2	I imagine that most winegrowers would be capable learn to use the application very quickly.			X	X						
		1	2	3	4						
3	I felt very confident when the robot was in automatic mode.				XX						
		1	2	3	4						
4	I found that all the information provided by application during mission monitoring were clear and sufficient.			X	X						
		1	2	3	4						
5	I find that all the information requested by the application were relevant.				XX						
		1	2	3	4						
6	I think that using automatic mode can lead to dangerous situations for me, the robot or the crops.	XX									
		1	2	3	4						
7	On a scale of 1 to 10, how do you feel you have mastered the application during the test?										
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
8	Is there any additional information that you would like to access via the application?	Storage of the latest speed and lift parameters for the mission, pre-recording and validation in the field Map of difficulties linked to the terrain (e.g. engine power)									
9	Are there any additional settings you'd like to be able to control directly from the application?										
10	Do you have any ideas for changes that you think would make the application easier to use?										

D1.9 Farmers perception on the proposed and running agricultural robotic systems (4)

		I totally disagree				I totally agree					
1	I think that being able to generate a new mission on plot could be useful to me frequently.	1	2	3	4	5					
2	I think that the mission generation platform is easy to use.	1	2	3	4	5					
3	I imagine that most winegrowers would be capable learn to use this platform very quickly.	1	2	3	4	5					
4	I find that all the information requested by the platform were relevant.	1	2	3	4	5					
5	I was sure I'd generated the mission I wanted by the of the test.	1	2	3	4	5					
6	On a scale of 1 to 10, how successful do you think master the platform during the test?	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
7	Would you prefer to be able to generate assignments yourself whenever you wanted, or would you prefer to have a technician carry out this action whenever necessary? Why or why not?										
8	Are there any additional parameters that you might have wanted to specify to bring the final mission closer to your expectations? If so, which ones?										
9	How do you think the platform could be improved to make it more practical or easier to use?										
10	Do you have any other comments about the mission generation platform: its use, problems encountered during the test, etc.?										

D1.9 Farmers perception on the proposed and running agricultural robotic systems (4)

		I totally disagree			I totally agree
1	I think the robot could be very useful to me frequently in my work.			XXXX	
		1	2	3	4
2	I think that using this robot would allow me to gain a lot of time in my job.				XXXX
		1	2	3	4
3	I think this robot does a better job than my usual tools.			XXXX	
		1	2	3	4
4	I think the robot is easy overall to get to grips with.			XX	
		1	2	3	4
5	I imagine that most winegrowers would be capable learn to use the robot very quickly.		X	XX	X
		1	2	3	4
6	I felt very confident using the robot.			XXXXX	
		1	2	3	4
7	The various pieces of information sent back to me make sure that the work goes well.			XX	
		1	2	3	4
8	I think that more advanced training to learn how to use the robot correctly and safely.				XXXX
		1	2	3	4
9	I think that a telephone helpline allowing me to contact a technician to sort out the problem. problems with the robot could come in handy a lot.			XX	XX
		1	2	3	4
10	How do you think the robot could be improved to make it easier to use?	1. Undercarriage / 6 tyres + Suspensions. 2. Tool detection 3. Remote supervision			

D1.9 Farmers perception on the proposed and running agricultural robotic systems (4)

11 What changes would you like to make to the robot to make it more effective in your work?

12 Would you be prepared to buy the robot in its current state to carry out your daily work? If not, what could change your mind?

Tracks and versatility
Trailing frame 1.4m

13 Finally, do you have any comments you would like to share with us?

Price too high but not shocking
The annual subscription price of €6,000 is too high
Guarantee only 1 to 3 years?